

is assigned to C-7 to C-10 protons. Another singlet at δ 7.4 is due to the C-5 and C-12 protons.

The molecular ion peaks for the compounds 3 are strong but those for 5 are not that strong, possibly because the dihydro compound may not be so stable¹⁵ at the heated inlet of the mass spectrometer. The major fragments for 3d appeared at m/z 325 (M^+ , 15%), 310 (15%), 297 (100%), 269 (20%), 192 (25%) and 166 (33%). The important peaks for 5b appeared at m/z 344 (M^+ , 10%), 209 (100%), 193 (15%), 167, 166 (75%). The peaks of minor importance are ignored.

A perusal of Table 2 reveals that almost all the compounds are ineffective against *P. vulgaris* (-), and moderately active against *B. subtilis* (+) and *S. aureus* (+). All the compounds tested were active against the fungi employed. Compounds 3b and 5b were more toxic than the others. Compounds 3c and 5a registered 60% inhibition at different dose levels.

References

1. G. THULLIER, J. LAVOREST, J. BONNET and J. THULLIER, *Eur. J. Med. Chem. Ther.*, 1975, 10, 87.
2. Y. TAKAHI, Jap. Pat. 74 125 529/1974 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 82, 150506).
3. K. W. WHEELER, L. NEDEBEC, A. PIERDET, F. LABRIE and J. BOISSIER, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, 1978; *J. Med. Chem.*, 1983, 25, 522.
4. J. ZSCHIEDRICH and F. THOMAS, Ger. Pat. 79 293/1972 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1972, 76, 14558).
5. R. HAWORTH and S. ROBINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 777.
6. H. JENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1948, 2, 91.
7. D. G. SMITH and S. ROBINSON, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1944, 57, 292.
8. K. KATAGIRI, Y. KUMURA, Y. WATANABE, E. HIDRO and T. MASAO, *Ser. C*, 1969, 16, 27.
9. V. G. KHUDENSKII and B. G. DISTANOV, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1967, 37, 2793.
10. E. SURENDER, R. BUCHI REDDY, P. BHAGWAN REDDY, G. V. P. CHANDRA MOULI and Y. D. REDDY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 534.
11. M. S. S. SHANKAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Kakatiya University, 1985.
12. F. ULLMANN and F. MAUTNER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1902, 35, 4802.
13. J. O. VINCENT and H. W. VINCENT, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1944, 55, 162.
14. ANONYMOUS, *Phytopathology*, 1947, 37, 854.
15. J. FIGUERAS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 808.

Synthesis of Newer 5-Chloro-2-phenylbenzimidazoles as Potential Antiviral Agents. Part-LIII

VIJAY A. SINGH and RAJENDRA S. VARMA*

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University,
Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 16 January 1987, revised 27 November 1987,
accepted 30 December 1987

VARIOUS benzimidazoles have been reported to possess antibacterial¹⁻³, antiviral⁴ and anthelmintic⁵ activities. These observations encouraged us to synthesise the title compounds and to screen them for antiviral activity.

2-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl)-5-chlorobenzimidazole (1) was synthesised by the reaction of 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine⁶ and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid in presence of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid⁷. 1 was treated with ethyl chloroacetate in dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate to yield ethyl-*p*-[2-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)]phenoxy acetate (2), which when further subjected to hydrazinolysis furnished *p*-[2-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)]phenoxyacetylhydrazine (3). 3 was refluxed with isatins and aromatic aldehydes to furnish 3-[2-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)-phenoxyacetylhydrazono]-2-indolinones (4) and *N*-(benzylidene)-*p*-[2'-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)]phenoxyacetylhydrazine (5).

The pmr spectrum of 5b was in accord with the assigned structure, δ 3.87 (3H, OCH_2), 4.82 (2H, $\text{OCH}_2\text{C}=\text{O}$), 6.8-8 (14H, NH, =CH and ArH); m/z 434/436 (M^+), 433/435 ($M-1$), 300/302, 243/245, 134, 133, 107, 102, 92 and 64.

Antiviral activity: Compounds 4 and 5 were screened for their antiviral activity against sunnhemp rosette virus (SRV) using the host *C. tetragonoloba* and tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) using the host *Datura stramonium* both *in vitro* and

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 5-CHLORO-2-PHENYLBENZIMIDAZOLES (4, 5)*

Compd. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)	Antiviral activity			
						% inhibition of SRV		% inhibition of TMV	
						<i>in vitro</i>	<i>in vivo</i>	<i>in vitro</i>	<i>in vivo</i>
4a	H	H	270	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₂ O ₂	15.4 (15.7)	94	Nil	48	16
4b	H	CH ₃	250	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂	15.0 (15.2)	58	34	26	24
4c	Cl	H	250	C ₁₀ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	14.7 (14.5)	42	35	53	33
4d	Cl	CH ₃	250	C ₁₁ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	14.0 (14.1)	54	50	58	37
4e	OH	H	250	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	15.0 (15.2)	57	32	48	30
4f	Br	H	250	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₂ Br	13.6 (13.8)	69	47	58	36
5a	H	H	155	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂	13.5 (13.8)	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
5b	OOH	H	152	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃	13.0 (12.8)	18	Nil	24	Nil
5c	H	OH	185	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₃	13.1 (13.3)	14	Nil	12	Nil

*Yields 55–65%; 4c $\nu_{\max}$ 3 800 (NH), 1 740 (C=O), 1 615 (C=N), 1 110 cm^{-1} (COO), and 5c 3 500 (OH), 3 800 (NH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N), 1 095 cm^{-1} (COO).

in vivo by the reported methods^{9,10}. Compounds 4c, 4d and 4f exhibited significant activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer spectrophotometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

2-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl)-5-chlorobenzimidazole (1): 4-Chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine (.1 mol), *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (.1 mol) and *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (0.2 mol) were heated at 210–20° for 2 h in an oil-bath. The cold contents were then basified with ammonia solution and the resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol, (70%), m.p. 270° (Found: N, 11.2. C₁₁H₉ClN₂O requires: N, 11.43%).

Ethyl-*p*-2-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)phenoxyacetate (2): Ethyl chloroacetate (0.01 mol) and 1 (0.01 mol) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and acetone were refluxed from 18 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from dilute methanol to yield 2 (80%), m.p. 112° (Found: C, 61.25; H, 4.40. C₁₇H₁₅ClN₂O₃ requires: C, 61.72; H, 4.52%).

***p*-2-(5-Chlorobenzimidazolyl)phenoxyacetylhydrazine (3)**: Ethyl-*p*-2-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)phenoxyacetate (2.50 g) and hydrazine hydrate (1 ml) in methanol (25 ml) were refluxed for 6 h. The resulting solid on cooling the reaction mixture was crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 248°.

3-[2-(5-Chlorobenzimidazolyl)phenoxyacetylhydrazono]-2-indolinones (4): Isatins (0.01 mol) and 3 (0.01 mol) in methanol (25 ml) containing glacial

acetic acid (1 drop) were refluxed for 4 h. The contents were cooled to room temperature and the resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol (Table I).

***N*-(Benzylidene)-*p*-[2'-(5-chlorobenzimidazolyl)]-phenoxyacetylhydrazine (5)**: A mixture of benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) and 3 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop) was refluxed for 6 h. The separated solid was recrystallised from methanol (Table I).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Chemistry Department and Head, Botany Department, Lucknow University, for facilities.

References

1. D. W. WOOLLEY, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1944, **152**, 225.
2. S. BAHADUR, A. K. GOEL and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1163.
3. S. BAHADUR, N. SRIVASTAVA, K. K. PANDEY and M. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 168.
4. R. L. THOMSON, *J. Immunol.*, 1947, **55**, 945.
5. P. PAOLO, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **93**, 220747.
6. Y. G. PRSIN and V. A. SERGEREV, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, **70**, 77875.
7. Y. TAKATA, M. TAO and K. YOKOTA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **92**, 94302.
8. H. N. VERMA and L. P. AWASTHI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 642.
9. G. W. SNEDCORE, "Statistical Methods", APP Ltd., Bombay, 1961.